

DJ HACKMAN AND G. OLDHAM'S WORK MOTIVATION MODEL

Saiyda Elmuratova

Óskinbeva Gulziyba

Karakalpak State University named after Berdak.

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Abstract. *This article discusses the work motivation model of J. Hackman and G. Oldham and its content-based nature.*

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Hackman and Oldham's Job Characteristics Theory suggests that high motivation is associated with experiencing three psychological states at work: Work meaningfulness. This work has meaning for you, is something you can relate to, and does not simply occur as a set of repetitive actions.

Furthermore, what are the 5 job characteristics model?

These five job characteristics are skill variety, task variety, task significance, autonomy, and judgment. Three different psychological states determine how an employee will respond to job characteristics: experienced meaningfulness, experienced responsibility for results, and knowledge of actual results.

The question may also arise: What are the 5 main job dimensions? There are five main dimensions of work: skill variety, task specificity, task significance, autonomy, and job feedback (PSU WC, 2015a, L. 10). A certain number of different skills require work.

The theory of work characteristics (theory of the main characteristics of work; theory of essential characteristics of work; theory of subjectively important characteristics of work) is one of the theoretical approaches to labor motivation of a descriptive type. The theory was proposed in the early 1970s by J. Heckman and G.R. Oldham. Scientists have identified five main characteristics of the content of the labor process, which, in their opinion, reflect a full understanding of the specifics of the employee's representation of the labor situation and affect the formation of his labor motivation.

According to one of the most common classifications of motivation theories in psychology, the job characteristics theory refers to substantive theories that emphasize the needs or factors that underlie motivation. This group also includes Maslow's pyramid of needs, McClelland's theory, K. Alderfer's theory of needs, and Herzberg's two-factor theory of motivation.

Similarly, what are the three main elements of the Hackman and Oldham model of job descriptions?

The three main elements that make up the Hackman and Oldham model of job characteristics.

Arrange the steps in a simple model of motivation from the beginning (top) to the end (bottom).

Unmet need.

Motivation.

Behavior.

Rewards.

Feedback.

Which of the following is one of the five main dimensions of jobs in the Hackman and Oldham model of job descriptions?

The five characteristics are skill variety, task personality, task significance, autonomy, and job judgment. The characteristics are combined with three psychological states to determine personal and work performance.

Classical growth theory suggests that economic growth will decline or cease as population increases and resources become scarce. According to classical growth theory economists, a temporary increase in real GDP per capita leads to a population explosion, which in turn reduces real GDP

Herbert Simon's model of decision-making. Nobel Prize-winning researcher Herbert Simon demonstrated that people go through three important stages in solving problems. He called these stages Intelligence, Design, and Choice. Decision-making can also be viewed as a type of problem-solving.

J. Hankman and J. Oldham developed and systematized Herzberg's ideas regarding methods of enriching work and increasing the motivational potential of work. According to the Hackman-Oldham model, high work motivation is determined by the following psychological states of workers:

Awareness of the meaning of work. If workers consider the work too simple (primitive) and purposeless, then motivation will be low. A sense of responsibility for the quality and quantity of manufactured products. Awareness of results. With feedback showing workers how well they perform the task, their motivation decreases. The psychological states of workers that determine the strength of work motivation cause the following main characteristics of work.

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Variety of the work process - the degree to which the performance of work requires solving various problems, using various knowledge, skills and abilities. For example, a secretary can perform a number of different tasks: take shorthand, work on a computer, answer phone calls, provide information to visitors, etc.

Task completion - the degree to which a job represents a complete cycle of operations, the execution of a task from start to finish. For example, a tailor would have a high degree of job completion if he or she performed all the work involved in making a suit (taking measurements, choosing materials, cutting, fitting, and sewing).

Task importance - the degree to which an employee perceives the importance of the tasks performed to others, the organization, or society. For example, the importance of the work of doctors who are searching for a cure for a serious disease would be very high.

These three factors contribute to the sense of meaningfulness of work. According to the job characteristics model, a job will be perceived as meaningful if it is seen as important, varied, and meaningful. Opportunity to demonstrate independence - the degree of freedom of the employee and the right to plan, determine the schedule of work, and make decisions about the method of their implementation. Independence in work makes employees feel a sense of personal responsibility for the results of their work. Employees themselves decide what and how they will do. Feedback - how timely and complete is the employee provided with information about his own effectiveness and the degree to which the results of work and work behavior correspond to established requirements.

An example of the organization of work in accordance with the model of key characteristics is the work of a surgeon. A surgeon is required to demonstrate a variety of skills and abilities in his work; his professional activity is distinguished by a high degree of completion, since he deals with the patient from the onset of the disease to its recovery (from diagnosis to surgery and treatment in the postoperative period), his work is of high importance (the life or death of the patient), he has a high degree of independence, since surgeons, as a rule, make independent decisions regarding the tactics of performing an operation; and he has clear and immediate feedback regarding the success of the operations performed.

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